

Methodological guidelines and reporting template for the 15 case studies in MATS

MATS Deliverable 3.1

MATS

making agricultural trade sustainable

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Summary

This document provides methodological and practical guidelines (incl. a common reporting template) for case study (CS) implementation, which are closely connected to previous, ongoing and future WP components (WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5). At the core of CS implementation is the process model underlying the analytical framework D2.4. and the resulting standardized CS reporting as outlined below. The mixed-methods approach implemented in MATS is to be adapted to the specific CS context, while a meaningful grouping of methods, tools and indicators across case studies contributes to comparability and cross-case consistency, and thus the overall systemic approach of MATS. The cases work jointly toward an overarching transition pathway (WP5), by developing individual impact pathways, while allowing for customized case-relevant assessments and coverage of additional sustainability indicators beyond core indicators uniting all cases. To translate these requirements into practice, the aim of D3.1. is to provide guidance for the implementation and standardized reporting of the case studies, and to ensure scientific value added over single case study methods approach and single case implementation. This value added is achieved when D3.1. is implemented in line with the analytical framework D2.4., which lays out the overarching inter-disciplinary methods framework and links to D3.1. through identical case implementation steps (Figure 4, D2.4.). The analytical framework D2.4. is thereby to be consulted in conjunction with D3.1., also to retain the connection between CS individual pathways and the overall impact pathway (connecting D2.2, D3.1 and WPs 4 & 5). At the practical level, the anticipated scientific value added is also expected to be achieved through mutual learning in a recursive and constantly updating process of case study implementation (joint workshops and zoom information sessions), and by obtaining methods synergies from group-wise CS implementation (groups of CS implementing the same methods approach, and same core sustainability indicators; learning from limitations and strengths of methods application; synergies from effective data exchange and data use across CSs and WPs), yet also achieved by making it explicit during CS implementation and in CS reporting which biases have been encountered and how they have been addressed in implementing the case studies.

The case studies are implemented in the period 1.7.2022 – 30.1.2024. A first draft report is to be submitted by 30.6.2023 for internal feedback. The final CS report is due 30.1.2024.

The two broad key questions for the 15 CSs in MATS are:

- 1). How do trade regimes, investments (esp. into agri-food value chains) and sustainability standards impact local, and, in some cases, national, and international socioeconomic and environmental conditions? and
- 2). How to foster the positive and reduce the negative impacts of agri-food trade and trade policy regimes on sustainable development and human rights?

In the implementation of CS, CS leads need to ensure that,

- data management is compliant with the EU's Guidelines on Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR) Data Management in Horizon 2020;
- all personal data are treated as strictly confidential and processed in compliance with General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679;
- anonymized data from surveys and interviews will be securely stored in a safe location at partners' facilities (internally, anonymized data may be shared) (see also the D7.4 'Data Management Plan' and Ds 8.1-8.3 'Ethical Requirements' on MS Teams);
- the identity of actors and researchers in case reporting is anonymized where this is deemed relevant to protect CS participants and researchers.

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² PU = Public, CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

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1. Introduction

The overall goal of WP3 is to provide a comprehensive assessment of the linkages between agricultural trade, investments, environmental sustainability and human well-being. WP3 is led by KE, and it comprises five Tasks (see Table 1).

TABLE 1. ROLES OF PARTNERS IN THE FIVE WP3 TASKS

Task	Lead	Co-lead	Supporting
3.1	UH	OXFAM	CRPA; UPM; FRAUNHOFER; UM-IGIR
3.2	UPM	OXFAM	UH; CRPA; SCiO; TNI; ESRF; NWU
3.3	KE	UPM	UH; SCiO; AUA
3.4	CRPA	NWU	ESRF; AUA
3.5	UH	UPM	ALL OTHER PARTNERS

Central to WP3 is a set of 15 in-depth case studies (CSs) which jointly implement the multi-methods, inter-disciplinary and systems approach that MATS is taking, while connecting especially WP2 (in particular D2.1 set of indicators, D2.3 the toolbox, and the analytical framework D2.4) with WP4 (institutional and legal frameworks) and WP5 (visioning & transition pathways). The aim of D3.1 is to provide guidance for the implementation and standardized reporting of the case studies, to ensure scientific value added over single case study methods approach and single case implementation, and to enable mutual learning across cases and cross-fertilization among the case studies. Through these D3.1 guidelines, MATS is aiming to achieve a balance between cross-case consistency/comparability (esp. with respect to sustainability indicators, impacts, methods) and within-case flexibility (esp. as a function of case-based phenomena, local actor or researcher needs including anonymity; specific data needs from other cases as inputs; specific needs to cover relevant sustainability indicators). In other words, through the D3.1 guidance, MATS aims to allow for some case-based plurality and diversity, that is balanced with an analysis-focused consolidation aim (i.e. grounding in D2.4) to identify and apply common cross-case cutting methods as part of MATS mixed methods approach, to apply common tools across cases (from

the MATS toolbox D2.3), to identify common biases, and to retain comparability via a common core sustainability indicator-focus that will be clarified further below. In settling for such a balance, we believe that the associated analytical process model underling D2.4 supports mutual learning and cross-fertilization among the case studies, an effective joint development of transition pathways, as well as a meaningful and synergistic joint analysis of all cases for achieving our goal of scientifically sound transition pathway design, and the subsequent delivery of sound policy recommendations.

1.1 Aims of the 15 in-depth case studies

All MATS case studies contribute to gaining a deeper understanding of the sustainability impacts of trade and trade regimes as they relate to institutional, regulatory, and legal frameworks (primarily: multilateral trading system, bilateral trade agreements, unilateral measures, Voluntary Sustainability Standards) at regional, national, and international levels. In order to connect the micro level (individual actor, local/ regional) to macro levels (national, international) the overarching key questions for MATS to be addressed in the CSs are:

1. How do trade regimes, investments (esp. into agri-food value chains) and/or sustainability standards impact local, and, in some cases, national, and international socioeconomic and environmental conditions? and
2. How to foster the positive and reduce the negative impacts of agri-food trade and trade policy regimes on sustainable development and human rights?

These guidelines aim to support the CS leaders to link their CS work with all relevant previous (WPs 1, 2) and subsequent work packages (WPs 4, 5, 6) and their related outcomes (incl. new initiatives relative to the GA, namely a discussion paper on CBAM (UH & UBERN-WTI) and a discussion paper on due diligence on deforestation free supply chains and green claims directive (UBERN-WTI & UH), with both discussion papers aiming to provide practical inputs for CS implementation, methods and data requirements). Central in this context is the extended analytical framework D2.4, which lays out the CS implementation steps in connection with the multi-methods approach (process model) and outlines the continuously recursive cross-case information and

methods feedback loops as part of workshops and informing sessions with a focus on case consistency, comparability and indicator focus.

1.2 Implementation

Critical and mandatory elements to all CSs:

The CSs are implemented as part of a constantly recursive / updating process (see D2.4 for the underlying process model that is both backward and forward-looking) by partners from the project consortium as well as by associated partner organizations. The case studies are implemented in the period 1.7.2022 – 30.1.2024. A first (internal) draft report is to be submitted until 30.6.2023 for feedback (UH, OSOL, CRPA, UPM, FRAUNHOFER, UM-IGIR). The final consolidated (public) CS report based on all individual CS following the CS reporting template below is due 30.1.2024.

To achieve a scientifically sound and practice-relevant outcome from all CSs that delivers on sustainability transition pathways and relevant policy recommendations, CSs are following standard research practice underlying a CS approach (Gioia, 2021; Langley & Meziani, 2020; Marshall & Rossman (2014); Merriam & Tisdell (2015); Strauss & Corbin, 2014; Yin, 2011, 2009) that is continuously translated to CS leaders through joint information and workshop sessions, and further detailed in the common reporting template below. As part of this approach and CS implementation, CS leaders are asked to follow the implementation steps spelled out in D2.4 (see esp. Fig. 4). To summarize, the structured CS implementation aims to allow for meaningful (phenomenon-driven) case-based plurality and diversity, which is balanced with an analysis-focused consolidation aim. This consolidation aim is put into practice by identifying and implementing appropriate common cross-case cutting methods, by applying common tools across cases (D2.3), by identifying and transparently sharing common biases, and by retaining cross-case comparability via focusing on a common core of sustainability indicators (see section 3.1., below).

The implementation of each case study analysis needs to be done in a way that the information requirements defined in the common reporting template can be met (see Section 3.2 below). Particular attention needs to be paid by all case studies to the process and assessment requirements (D2.4) and also

the information requirements related to WP4 (see Section 2.3.1) and WP5 (Section 2.3.2).

Each case study lead needs to ensure that their research complies with WP7 and WP8, in particular:

1. data management is compliant with the EU's Guidelines on Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR) Data Management in Horizon 2020[3];
2. all personal data will be treated as strictly confidential and processed in compliance with General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679;
3. anonymized data from surveys and interviews will be securely stored in a safe location at partners' facilities (internally, anonymized data may be shared) (see also the D7.4 'Data Management Plan' and Ds 8.1-8.3 'Ethical Requirements' stored on MS Teams of MATS);
4. the identity of actors and researchers is in case reporting where this is deemed relevant protected and anonymized.

Our expectation is that the balance between cross-case methodological diversity and cross-case commonality on analysis and indicator focus through D3.1 guidance will ensure a scientifically rigorous and policy-relevant joint analysis of the agricultural trade policy regimes, practices, investments and sustainability standards considered relevant by MATS. At the same time, this balanced CS implementation approach will contribute with transferable insights into the strengths and weaknesses of different methods and implementation processes (see D2.4), thereby contributing to future analyses beyond MATS (see also 'MATS Trade Hub' D6.3 and D2.3).

Comparability and homogeneity across CSs will be ensured at a higher level through the implementation steps laid out in D2.4 (extended analytical framework and underlying process model; interdisciplinary approach that connects to systems thinking), and through conveying a common understanding of the CS approach (Gioia, 2021; Langley & Meziani, 2020; Strauss & Corbin, 2014; Yin, 2011, 2009) as part of ongoing workshops and information sessions. Comparability and homogeneity across CS are further established (a.) with respect to the core coverage of sustainability indicators

across all CS, and (b.) with respect to cross-CS sharing and identification of biases (see below for more details on (a.) and (b.)).

Clustering and connections across CS are supported through continuous joint workshops on methods and WP-interconnections, as well as through an integrated data exchange (i.e., data output from several cases, identifying for example measures of labor conditions and thus competitiveness, become data input for other CS, with regard to their needs for modeling, for institutional/legal analysis or sustainability transition pathway analysis). This focus on WP-interconnections and on integrated data-exchange is expected to contribute to creating desired cross-case synergies beyond the joint analysis coverage of core indicators and commodities (e.g., several CSs cover a given commodity from the perspective of different regional or sustainability dimensions). Furthermore, to retain practical actor and policy relevance and societal legitimacy (see WP5, common sustainability transition pathways), CSs will be working directly with stakeholder organizations by enabling them to provide feedback on ongoing CS implementation, and to engage in policy dialogues (WP6).

1.3 Additional analyses performed in some case studies

Some of the analyses will only be performed in a smaller number of CSs, while this clustering will contribute to the robustness of models and CS implementation:

- Customized system dynamics models are created for CS #3, #5 and #14 to explore interdependencies and impacts across scales (micro/macro). In the context of implementing these models, CSs will explore in how far qualitative causal loop diagrams and quantitative (e.g., CGE, system dynamics and spatially explicit) models can be applied also in other CSs, for example to generate estimates and forecasts of outcomes across sectors, economic actors, dimensions of development, over time and space (Task 3.3 led by KE).
- In CS #10, #11 and #13, an in-depth assessment is performed of environmental and social sustainability impacts in agri-food value chains

relating to trade, while assessing trade-offs among sustainability impacts and competitiveness implications. The analysis focuses in particular on labor costs and environmental legislation while connecting to other case studies through the application of common tools from the toolbox D2.3 (e.g., applying the Global Reporting Initiative to connect and translate high-level sustainability indicators/ SDGs with national/ commodity-based measures of labor standards; see Langeneck & Steiner, 2022).

The leaders of Tasks 3.3 (KE) and 3.4 (CRPA) are responsible for providing guidance, and for assuring effective linkages, feedback-loops and collaboration with those CS that contribute to these tasks.

2. Methodological guidelines for the 15 in-depth case studies

2.1 Broad guidance

The following methodological guidance builds on the results of T2.1, T2.3 and T2.4, and the eight case implementation steps described in D2.4 that apply to all case implementations (D2.4, section 3.1, in particular Figures 3 & 4). With the guidelines here we do not prescribe and predetermine one common impact pathway prior to CS implementation, but instead we derive a set of individual case-based pathways as part of the process model that underlies D2.4, connecting the individual case and institutional frameworks (WP3, WP4) with the back-casting and visioning (WP5), so that a 'common set of aligned pathways' is arising from the CS implementation. More specifically, the case studies develop and analyze their own impact pathways, as a function of the diversity of commodity, region, methods and sustainability indicator focus. Through the guidelines here, we do not mandate the use of the same methods/models across all case studies, yet as it is evident from the process model and multi-methods approach underlying D2.4, we ensure that:

- i. all cases align to the same high-level impact pathway as described in the deliverable 2.4, also through close collaborations across WPs, especially with WP5 (a unified impact pathway in MATS is derived from a set of individual case-based pathways, using a bottom-up approach, via the implementation of the analytical framework described in D2.4),
- ii. all cases follow the same implementation steps (see Figures in D2.4), and follow the same standard case study methods guidance (see Gioia, 2021; Langley & Meziani, 2020; Yin, 2011, 2009),
 - we consider a CS as an interactive set of people, structures, and processes that need to be explained (Gioia, 2021: 21).
 - transferability across a CS implies that even a single observation can represent a principle that applies to many different contexts (Gioia, 2021: 21).

- we should not presumptively impose our understanding on their [informants] understanding (Gioia, 2021: 22),
 - any good interpretive CS should generate a plausible, defensible explanation of some phenomenon of interest (Gioia, 2021: 27).
 - for definitions of design, collection of data and different types of analyses under qualitative methods, please consult Berg (2012), Norman & Lincoln (2000), as summarized here: <https://libguides.usc.edu/writingguide/qualitative>
- iii. all cases report on the same five sustainability dimensions (with a varying set of sustainability indicators within each dimension, as a function of the case-specific context) that were identified as part of a process guided by UPM (D2.2). Since each case study will have a different 'pathway to indicator-specific sustainability', each will have its own list of key indicators, while retaining common grounds for deriving a common impact pathway (WP5) through a common coverage of the five sustainability dimensions that were identified as relevant across cases (Policy, governance, and regulations; Human capital; Social Capital; Environmental / Natural Capital; Economy and markets). Thereby, we ensure that each CS reports on a comprehensive set of sustainability dimensions that contain a core set of overlapping indicators, while allowing each case to cover additional indicators beyond the core indicator set, as a function of commodity, region, and methods-focus of a case. More specifically:
- Based on a prioritization process led by UPM (D2.1), a list of 27 indicators, 5 per dimension (Policy, governance, and regulations; Human capital; Social Capital; Environmental / Natural Capital; Economy and markets), with 7 in the economy dimension given its nuances across case studies, was identified.
 - In the process leading to D3.1., the CS leaders agreed on providing this list of 27 (5+5+5+5+7), so case studies are able to discard indicators within each dimension that (a.) may not be relevant to their case, and/or (b.) they might not have data on, and still report on all the 5 dimensions.

- The case reporting template (below, as part of D3.1) specifies that cases can report within a range in terms of a minimum of 3 indicators per dimension, so 15 altogether.

As a result of the above process of indicator selection and prioritization with the MATS consortium members, the overall MATS approach – as also reflected in the analytical framework D2.4 - will ensure that the analysis is systemic and covers all key elements of sustainable development relevant for MATS.

Furthermore, the mixed methods approach (qualitative & quantitative) implies that for some parts of the CS analysis quantitative data will be analyzed, while in other cases, we work with expert views, best professional judgements, focus groups and online surveys. Through this mixed-methods approach we expect to obtain a better understanding of the linkages between broader sustainability (social, environmental), investment and human wellbeing issues and the institutional, legal and regulatory frames impacting agri-food trade. The linkages relate to commodities, actors, and stakeholders along value-chains, as well as to spatial and temporal dimensions, and are relevant when CS are,

- identifying the key actors with their roles, interests and responsibilities, and explore how to address risks and implications of power inequality, participation, and public interests in local and global agri-food value chains;
- taking a human rights perspective in this analysis that allows to identify roles of rightsholders and duty bearers, with science informing the political choices to be made;
- examining the extent and role of transparency in agri-food chains (including pricing, production and investment information transmission, sustainability standards transparency); digitalization, for example, carries the potential to deal with greenwashing and to create trust for consumers into sustainability claims in trade and value chains, potentially leading to a shift in demand, thereby triggering a lasting and self-sustaining transition to improved sustainability (see also D2.4: Section 4.3).

CS leads have at their disposal the 'Sustainable trade toolbox' (D2.3). It comprises 114 instruments that range from guiding principles and approaches

to specific methods, tools (such as value chain analysis, use of GRI) and indicator sets. To achieve cross-case comparability, methods clustering, and mutual learning from such clustering, CS leads are instructed to use tools, indicators and guidance from this toolbox, and employ them within the extended analytical framework D2.4. For this purpose, D2.4 also mentions keywords that can be used for searching the toolbox and identifying CS-relevant tools. The selection of tools and the application of them will be discussed in zoom information sessions and workshops planned during 2023.

The CS are envisaged to be clustered according to the following methods, contributing further to cross-case comparability and consistency (see D2.4 for further detail):

- 1). Value chain mapping and analysis (#1, #2, #8, #10, #13);
- 2). Participatory qualitative research approaches including semi-structured key informant interviews, online and household surveys, and focus group discussions (#1, #2, #4, #6, #7, #8, #9, #11, #12, #15);
- 3). Analysis of publicly available macro-economic statistics, current legislations, existing studies, and triangulation (#2, #6, #8, #12, #15);
- 4). Analysis of publicly available economic, agricultural, environmental and climate statistics and existing studies (#3).

In light of the emphasis on MATS on social sustainability indicators and implications, CS leads are instructed to cover labor, human rights and gender issues and dimensions where applicable. For CS that analyze human rights and gender issues related to agri-food trade and impacts, Oxfam is providing guidance documents that will be presented in information sessions with UPM, and further discussed by UBERN-WTI and UM: <https://hria.oxfam.org/> and <https://policy-practice.oxfam.org/resources/quick-guide-to-gender-analysis-312432/>

All CSs include different levels and forms of engagement with key actors shaping agricultural trade, as well as with organizations who are anticipated to be able to use the research results to address sustainability challenges in the trade context (for example as part of focus groups, workshops to obtain feedback on ongoing research or preliminary findings). The envisaged stakeholder engagement will ensure that analyses are meaningful and

applicable in different contexts, and it will help to derive concrete policy recommendations as part of the sustainability transition paths analysis. These key actor engagement activities complement those spelled out in Task 6.3 'Facilitate a civil society-stakeholder-policy dialogue', led by the OXFAM team (i.e., OSOL and OWW).

In conducting CS work and CS reporting, CS leads are requested that different forms of biases are acknowledged and made transparent: each case study is therefore tasked (also as part of the case study reporting form) to specify which biases are perceived to apply during case study design and implementation (including biases in selecting the set of indicators, biases from selecting particular actors, from participating actors, and from methods implementation such as semi-structured interviews). Potential biases will be discussed in workshops and information sessions, and the case study literature can be consulted further on this matter (see below, Annex 1 – References).

2.2 Visualization of impact pathways

The visualization of individual-case impact pathways will help to clarify case-based interrelationships (trade regimes, investments, sustainability impacts; at micro- and macro-levels), also contributing to visualize the CS results, and thereby contributing to deriving the common sustainability transition pathways analysis (WP5, back-casting, visioning). In particular, the implementation of Causal Loop Diagrams (CLDs) is encouraged for each case in conjunction with T3.3 and will thus be supported through information sessions and workshops (KE, UPM).

To introduce CS leads to impact pathways visualization, the following examples are available for consultation:

- Logical Diagrams to explain connections and impact pathways; examples include:

<https://valuingvoices.com/>

Springer-Heinze, A., Hartwich, F., Henderson, J. S., Horton, D., & Minde, I. (2003). Impact pathway analysis: an approach to strengthening the

impact orientation of agricultural research. *Agricultural systems*, 78(2), 267-285.

Douthwaite, B., & Hoffecker, E. (2017). Towards a complexity-aware theory of change for participatory research programs working within agricultural innovation systems. *Agricultural systems*, 155, 88-102.

- the UN Capital Development Fund provides examples of a mapping of impact pathways (see <https://www.unCDF.org/impact-pathways/home> and <https://www.unCDF.org/Download/AdminFileWithFileName?id=12318&cultureId=127&filename=impact-pathways-methodology.pdf>) ;
- KUMU is a mapping software that helps to organize complex data into relationship maps: <https://kumu.io/>

CS leads are further encouraged to consult the visualization of linkages elaborated in D1.1, (p. 34) to support case-based visualization adaptation:

FIGURE 1. THE VISUALIZATION OF LINKAGES ELABORATED IN D1.1 (P.34)

Following the implementation of impact pathways visualization at each CS as a function of the visualization tool that is deemed best fitting by the CS leads, it is envisaged that particularly powerful examples of the visualization of

impact pathways from the CS will be featured in the project's communication channels (WP6).

2.3 Meeting the needs of WP4 and WP5

2.3.1 WP4 Institutional, regulatory and legal frameworks

The overall goal of WP4 is to gain a better understanding of the role of institutional, regulatory, and legal frameworks (IRLs) for agricultural trade, and identify how these frameworks relate to the impacts of agricultural trade on sustainability (SDGs). By integrating the IRL analysis in the case studies with the development of the transition pathways (WP5), the systemic approach of MATS aligns also with Policy Coherence for Sustainable Development (PCSD) adopted in WP4 (see D2.4).

For implementing WP4, each CS is tasked to provide output for WP4 through an analysis of secondary data, through fieldwork (semi-structured interviews, focus groups, questionnaire), or through modeling (see D2.4), so that the following questions can be answered by WP4:

A. Defining trade regimes

Each case study explicitly defines what is the relevant "trade regime". To ensure that all case studies apply the same understanding and relevant terminology regarding "trade regimes", please use the following questions in defining the relevant regime. This task is important to increase comparability and coherence across the 15 case studies. "Trade regimes" is one of the critical common denominators for the CS and further MATS analysis. This will also contribute to the collection of information for the deliverable WP4 - Institutional, regulatory, and legal frameworks and prepare for the development of transition pathways in WP5.

A first task for CS leads is therefore: Define the relevant trade regime for your case study. Which of the following trade regime(s) is most important and relevant for your case study?

- 1). Multilateral trading system which refers to the World Trade Organization - in particular The WTO Agreement on Agriculture, WTO Agreement of Sanitary and Phytosanitary (SPS) measures, Technical Barriers to Trade (TBT) Agreement, WTO Trade Facilitation Agreement) and other agricultural

trade-related agreements: Agreement on Rules of Origin, Agreement on Import Licensing Procedures, Agreement on Customs Valuation, Agreement on Pre-shipment Inspection and agriculture in Regional Trade Agreements (RTAs) see for more https://www.wto.org/english/tratop_e/tratop_e.htm)

- 2). Bilateral trade relations such as regional trade agreements/free trade agreements (RTAs/FTAs) such as AfCFTA or EU-Economic Partnership Agreements (EPAs)/Association Agreements (AAs) with African countries (see e.g., https://trade.ec.europa.eu/doclib/docs/2022/february/tradoc_160053.pdf).
- 3). Unilateral measures set by countries (national regulation to be complied with to satisfy market access conditions) such as the EU due diligence legislation on forced labour or deforestation? These can be any regulatory measures defined in national legislation that impede market access and trade. Also the EU's Generalized System of Preferences (GSP) framework is a unilateral measure (see https://policy.trade.ec.europa.eu/development-and-sustainability/generalised-scheme-preferences_en) and the Everything But Arms scheme: <https://trade.ec.europa.eu/access-to-markets/en/content/everything-arms-eba>
- 4). Voluntary Sustainability Standards (VSS) which comprise of private certification schemes, labeling programs and private standards (see e.g., https://unctad.org/system/files/official-document/ditctab2021d2_en.pdf)
- 5). If none of the above, identify specific domestic government measures that have a bearing on achieving the sustainable development outcomes for your CS and that have a linkage to trade e.g., via forming a market access barrier.

B. Identifying relevant investment measures

Where feasible (taking into account the need to preserve anonymity of respondents and the sensitivity of financial information, as well as the relative importance of investment / financial issues compared to social and/ or environmental issues), CS leads are tasked to try and assess the relevance of production, processing, transport or infrastructure-related investment issues (barriers and promoters), including measures that relate to investment

facilitation, investment-related subsidies and incentives, investment screening, pre-entry or post-entry discriminatory treatment of investments/investors. In this way, insights are sought for assessing inbound investments, local engagement and local conditions (e.g., local discrimination in the access to household/ micro-credit as a function of gender or farm size/ type) against foreign investments affecting the sustainability of agricultural trade. More specifically CS leads are tasked to identify investment measures,

- adopted by a government (as opposed to private initiatives, such as private standards imposed by a company in the value chain, voluntary labeling of products, private contracts);
- at any level of government (e.g., EU, national, regional, local);
- in import or export markets (e.g., in the EU, or in the country of origin);
- already adopted (existing measures) or under consideration (proposals).

Furthermore, CS leads are tasked to identify whether / which trade and sustainability related investments are relevant for their CS:

- i. Identify whether Aid-for-Trade and Official Development Assistance (ODA) is relevant in your CS: (https://www.wto.org/english/tratop_e/devel_e/a4t_e/aid4trade_e.htm and https://www.wto.org/english/tratop_e/devel_e/a4t_e/a4t_fact-sheet_e.htm and <https://www.oecd.org/dac/financing-sustainable-development/development-finance-standards/official-development-assistance.htm><https://www.oecd.org/dac/financing-sustainable-development/development-finance-standards/official-development-assistance.htm>)
- ii. Identify specific private initiatives (e.g., private product standards, labelling, contracts) that have a bearing on achieving the sustainable development outcomes for your CS.
- iii. Identify specific international investment, or environmental rules that you believe have a bearing on achieving the sustainable development outcomes for your CS. This could include international rules in Bilateral Investment Treaties (BITs), Multilateral Environ-

mental Agreements (MEAs) (e.g., UNFCCC, Paris Agreement, Convention on Biological Diversity). If you are not aware of any of these specific international rules, UM-IGIR will investigate this as part of WP4; and,

- iv. If possible, develop hypotheses around, and, potentially, test, the impact on the sustainable development outcomes for your CS of the specific domestic measures identified under (a); the private initiatives under (b); and/or the international rules under (c).

C. Identify the relevance of IP Rights

To identify the relevance of IP rights in the context of a given case study, with the objective to identifying their cross-case relevance, please CS leads consider the following:

- i. If possible, identify the relevant jurisdictions in which IP rights have been obtained in relation to products relevant for your CS (e.g., geographical indication, trademarks, plant variety protection, supplementary protection certifications, patents, trade secrets) and which entity owns the right;
- ii. If possible, identify which technologies the product/process relies on and whether it is available to producers and under which conditions (licensing, royalties); and,
- iii. If possible, explore what the short and mid-term plans are for using technology for relevant products in the CS.

2.3.2 WP5 Transition pathways and policy recommendations

The overall goal of WP5 is to derive transition pathways for desirable changes in trade relations and practices at macro, meso and micro level, to identify suitable instruments, and to formulate corresponding policy recommendations. A visioning process focused on alternative trade regimes and practices will lead to the formulation of the common orientation of all case studies with regard to the most important issues in sustainable trade and desirable developments in the future (see also D2.4: Section 4.4).

WP5 builds on and is carried out in close cooperation with WP4 related to institutional, regulatory and legal frameworks (incl. WTO compatibility) and

with WP6 in engaging with civil-society actors, trade and value-chain actors, and policymakers. It is envisaged that some of the actors and stakeholders identified and interviewed as part of the CS will be employed for the transition pathway development analysis (in particular the road-mapping exercises).

Key questions to be covered in each case study report related to WP5 include:

- What are key determinants for change, and topics in each CS (commodity, value-chain, region), shaping future developments and sustainability impacts?
 - How are (which) indicators supporting future developments?
 - Categorizing key determinants/topics using the PESTEL categories (Issa et al., 2010): political, economic, social, technological, environmental, and legal.
- What are signals for change already visible today, confirming the direction of change (e.g., acceptance of new technologies in primary production, 'smartification' of the value chain, diffusion of e-commerce in the food sector)?
- Which key stakeholders/ organizations can be involved (and are likely to be available) in the foresight process?

3. Common reporting template for the 15 case studies

The common set of core indicators and the common reporting template presented in this section are aimed at ensuring consistency and comparability across case studies, while retaining case-based flexibility (see section 1 introduction, above, for further rationale).

3.1 Common set of core indicators

One feature of MATS is a common set of core sustainability indicators across five sustainability dimensions. These indicators were identified initially as part of D2.1 to be meaningful to all CSs in a process of expert (and CS team members) solicitation and prioritization, and they have been checked for accuracy and relevance in subsequent information meetings and workshops coordinated by UPM. Since each case study will have an individual alias different 'pathway to indicator-specific sustainability', each CS can have its own list of key indicators. However, for retaining common grounds also for deriving a common impact pathway (WP5) through a common coverage of the five sustainability dimensions that were identified as relevant across cases (Policy, governance, and regulations; Human capital; Social Capital; Environmental / Natural Capital; Economy and markets), a core set of three indicators per sustainability dimension has to be reported on by each CS.

In light of the systems focus of MATS, all indicators and sustainability dimensions defined as "core" as per below will contribute to assessing linkages between agricultural trade, investments, environmental sustainability and human well-being (see also Figure 1 in D1.1; D2.1; and Section 3 and Annex 1 in D2.4), and where feasible also assessing the key trade-offs among these sustainability dimensions at the level of each CS.

- Based on a prioritization process led by UPM (D2.1), the list of 56 indicators were reduced to a list of 27 indicators, five indicators per sustainability dimension (Policy, governance, and regulations; Human capital; Social Capital; Environmental / Natural Capital; Economy and markets), with two additional ones, i.e. seven indicators in the economy dimension, given its

diversity in relevance across case studies, was identified, and needs to be reported by each CS. To define the indicators to be included in the final list two main criteria have been followed: (1) the 20 indicators with higher rate from experts and CS leaders; (2) at least 5 indicators per dimension:

FIGURE 2. THE TOP 20 INDICATORS WITH HIGHER RATE FROM EXPERTS AND CS LEADERS IN D2.1

- In the process leading to D3.1, the CS leaders agreed on providing this list of 27 (5+5+5+5+7), so case studies are able to discard indicators within each dimension that (a.) may not be relevant to their case, and/or (b.) they might not have data on, and still report on all the 5 sustainability dimensions.
- The case reporting template (below) specifies that cases can report within a range in terms of a minimum of 3 indicators per dimension, so 15 altogether.

3.2 Format and section headings of CS reporting template

To contribute to our deliverable in terms of the single final Case Study Report under the GA of MATS, all CSs will follow the length and heading guidelines as per below, keeping in mind the goals of consistency, comparability and systems-focus applying to all case studies. As a rough rule of thumb, each case study is to aim at a minimum of about 30 to 40 pages core text yet varying as a function of the empirical approach and the need to include data, photos or other appendices.

Executive summary

- the executive summary should be between 5 and maximum 10% length of the length of your entire case study report
- please follow the instructions here: <https://libguides.usc.edu/writingguide/executivesummary>

(1) Introduction

- provide an introduction that builds on your initial CS description, yet also documents the evolution of your CS, and the connection to other CS (incl. methods grouping with other CS, overlaps on commodities, regions etc. in other CS) and WPs, as part of the process of developing and implementing your CS
- introduce briefly the objectives and research questions (coverage of indicators, key indicator / sustainability dimension focus etc.)
- the introduction should be approximately 10% of your total report

(2) Objectives and analytical approach

Brief description of specific objectives and methodology used for the case study, including data collection and analysis, following these headings:

2.1. Objectives and scope of the CS

- describe the relevant key features of trade policy regimes, investments in agri-food value chains, and sustainability standards applicable to your CS
- describe the key impacts of agri-food trade on sustainable development and on human rights you deem relevant in your CS
- describe the key linkages you deem relevant in your CS: From trade policy regime, investments and sustainability standards to impacts; provide a short description based on the common set of core indicators plus case-study specific indicators chosen

2.2. Literature

- literature and gaps, conjectures / hypotheses arising from the literature and previous studies (gray literature)
- for guidance see here: <https://libguides.usc.edu/writingguide/literaturereview>

2.3. Methods

- importance of a good methodology section, and how to write it: <https://libguides.usc.edu/writingguide/methodology>
- for definitions of design, collection of data and different types of analyses under qualitative methods, please consult Berg (2012), Norman & Lincoln (2000), as summarized here: <https://libguides.usc.edu/writingguide/qualitative>

2.4. Data description

2.5. Data analysis

(3) Results, discussion and limitations

for guidance on writing the results, discussion and limitations sections, see here: <https://libguides.usc.edu/writingguide/results>

3.1. Results and discussion

- Include a statement that clarifies possible linkages between the 5 sustainability dimensions, and possible interaction effects you identified between (sub)indicators (e.g. identifying a positive impact with regard to social sustainability indicators, while finding at the same time a negative impact with regard to environmental sustainability indicators).
- Include here a visual representation and discussion of the case-specific impact pathways: Visualization and identification of key leverage points in agri-food trade/impact system applicable to your CS
- Include here a description of actors and gender-issues relevant in the context of your CS: key actors with their roles, interests and responsibilities; gender issues; how to address issues of power inequality, participation, and public interests.

- Include here a description and discussion of the role of national and supranational legal and policy frameworks with particular attention paid to the EU and the WTO as applicable (information required for WP4) (optional: to respond to D.2.3. you could prepare a political economy mapping of the different protagonists, including WTO rules, FTA, national authorities, local actors, private sector, donors).
- Discuss your individual lessons learned as a research team, also in terms of mutual learning with other CS during workshops etc., synergies encountered with other CS, or unexpected hindrances.

3.2. Limitations

here please also report all biases here that you have encountered / expect to be relevant in the design and implementation of your CS; for possible limitations / biases of the researcher to report on, and for a discussion of possible methodological limitations, see here: <https://libguides.usc.edu/writingguide/limitations>

(4) Key conclusions and policy recommendations

outline key determinants/topics for each case study shaping future developments and sustainability impacts; ways forward; recommendations on fostering the positive and reducing the negative impacts of agri-food trade (information required by WP5; see Section 2.3.2)

(5) References

your list of references here; please cite consistently in APA format (so that we can then also accumulate all references for the single case study report to be submitted as DL) - guidance for citation style to be found here: <https://libguides.usc.edu/writingguide/citingsources>

(6) Appendices

4 Annex 1 – References

- Berg, B. L. (2001). *Qualitative research methods for the social sciences*. Allyn & Bacon.
- Denzin, N. K., & Lincoln, Y. S. (Eds.). (2011). *The Sage handbook of qualitative research*. Sage.
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https://www.academia.edu/13784473/Case_study_research_design_and_methods_4th_ed_Robert_Yin
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5 Annex 2

TABLE 2. THE 15 CASE STUDIES IN MATS

<https://sustainable-agri-trade.eu/case-studies-overview/>

Topic	Key aspects	Main locus	Lead partner
1) Effects of trade on commercialisation and processing of food products	Improving the livelihoods of smallholder farmers through trade and food value chains; localisation of food systems, strengthening of territorial markets	Uganda, Tanzania	University Helsinki (UH), John Sumelius, with Makerere University and Moshi Co-operative University
2) Trade, resilience and social sustainability: oats value chains in the Nordics	Resilience of trade-dependent food value chains in the context of intra-EU agri-food trade and social sustainability; sustainability and equity	Finland, Sweden, EU	University Helsinki (UH), Bodo Steiner
3) Trade, sustainability and environmental linkages in Finnish dairy production	Mapping the linkages of dairy production and dairy trade with environmental externalities and production of ecosystem services	Finland, EU, trade partners	University Helsinki (UH), Nina Hyytiä, Antony Starr
4) Accessing export markets with high quality/social/environmental standards	Standards and market access; challenges related to WTO Rules and Regulations and/or EU requirements; strengthening of territorial markets	Sub-Saharan Africa	Economic and Social Research Foundation (ESRF), Hoseana Bohela Lunogelo, with University of Dar-es-Salaam
5) Role of agricultural inputs and policy regulation in sustainable value chains	Emerging markets; poultry chains; role of policy regulation regarding animal welfare, inputs and trade; competitiveness, sustainability, livelihoods	Ghana	Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Pablo Vidueira, with CSIR – Science and Technology Policy Research Institute
6) Farm gate prices and sustainable business models: towards living income	Experiences, obstacles, impact and lessons learned from a multi-stakeholder initiative on sustainability standards in the cacao sector	EU, Côte d’Ivoire	Oxfam Wereldwinkels (OWW), Bart Van Besien
7) Impacts of EU policies on local dairy value chains in Africa	EU agricultural, trade, investment and development policies; impact on the development of local, fair and sustainable dairy chains	EU, Africa	Oxfam Solidarité - Oxfam Solidariteit (OXFAM), Thierry Kesteloot

Topic	Key aspects	Main locus	Lead partner
8) EU climate and energy policies and their influence on trade and land use	EU biofuel policies and mandates; sustainability criteria biofuels; EU climate funding, carbon markets, offset mechanism; palm oil; land use change	EU, America, Africa, Asia	Oxfam Solidarité - Oxfam Solidariteit (OXFAM), Alba Saray Pérez-Terán
9) Human rights and environmental due diligence in the coffee value chain	Integrating human rights and environmental due diligence in coffee chains; impact on production practices and smallholder farmers	Tanzania, Bu-rundi, Ugan-da, Ethiopia	Oxfam Wereldwinkels (OWW), Sarah Vaes
10) Beef and policy coherence for sustainable development	EU agricultural, trade, investment and development policies; impact on local, fair, sustainable beef chains, including consumers and retailers	EU, Africa, South America	Research Centre on Animal Production (CRPA), Alberto Menghi, with Agribenchmark Beef
11) Private standards and sustainable trade	Impact of processors/retailers' standards on development of local, fair, sustainable food chains; GLOBAL G.A.P.	Africa, Asia	Research Centre on Animal Production (CRPA), Alberto Menghi, with Global G.A.P
12) Ethical trade initiatives in the South African wine industry	Assessment of local and global ethical trade programmes in South Africa (e.g. Fair Trade, Ethical Trading Initiative, Ethical Trade Association)	South Africa, trade partners	North-West University (NWU), Ernst Idsardi, with Stellenbosch University
13) Dairy production, standards and competitiveness in global markets	Labour costs; additional costs resulting from environmental regulation; total production costs; processing and retail	EU, Africa, America	Research Centre on Animal Production (CRPA), Alberto Menghi, with International Farm Comparison Network (IFCN)
14) Changing land-use trajectories due to the EU-Mercosur trade agreement	The case of pork exports from Brazil to the EU: trade agreements, EU-Mercosur; pork value chains, soya and palm oil production; deforestation.	EU, Brazil	Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Pablo Vidueira, with Institute for Agriculture and Trade Policy (IATP)
15) The new generation of EU Free Trade Agreements (FTAs) and their impacts	Impact of EU-Tunisia FTA on incomes and market opportunities for farmers, fishers, breeders; ecological resilience, especially water scarcity	EU, N Africa (Tunisia)	Transnational Institute (TNI), Pietje Vervest, with Tunisian Observatory of the Economy